

IPERION HS

CALL: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1

GA n. 871034

D.6.3 Final report on innovation, exploitation and interoperability

Lead Author: Adam Gibson

Co-authors: Marta Castillejo, Paula Carmona, Demetrios Anglos, Polonca Ropret, Roxana Radvan, Joseph Padfield, Wim Fremout, Wolfgang Schmidle, Sophia Sotiropoulou

Document information

Project number	871034	Acronym	IPERION HS
Full title	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science		
Project url	www.iperionhs.eu		
EU Project Officer	António Ventura		

Deliverable	Number	D.6.3	Title	Final report on innovation, exploitation and interoperability
Work Package	Number	6	Title	Innovation and Exploitation

Deliverable nature	<input type="checkbox"/> prototype <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> report <input type="checkbox"/> demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> other		
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential <input type="checkbox"/> Restricted		
Contractual delivery date	(30/03/2023)		
Actual delivery date	(30/03/2023)		
Status	Version 1.0	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final	

Authors (Partner)	Adam Gibson (UCL)			
Responsible Author	Name	Adam Gibson	Email	adam.gibson@ucl.ac.uk
	Partner	UCL	Phone	+44 (0)20 7679 0279

Total number of pages	34
Keywords	Innovation; Exploitation; interoperability; data management plan; FAIR data;

Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev. no.	Author	Change
08/02/2023	0.1	AG	Outline only
17/02/2023	0.2	AG	Draft Innovation section
20/03/2023	0.3	AG	Full first draft
28/03/2023	0.9	AG, JP, PR	Final draft
30/03/2023	1.0	AG	Final version

Abstract

This deliverable addresses the complex interactions of innovation, exploitation and interoperability in IPERION HS and their contributions to E-RIHS. It is based on work carried out in T6.1 (Innovation), T6.3 (Interoperability) and T6.4 (Exploitation) and draws heavily on the interim deliverables produced by those Tasks. The information was obtained by carrying out surveys, interviews, examination of previous publications and by the development of a data management plan. The work was carried out to support IPERION HS, but here we also examine the implications for E-RIHS ERIC.

The main conclusion is that Heritage Science and E-RIHS exists within its own ecosystem, but to maximise its impact, it needs to engage with a wide range of other, related interests. This involves engaging with new user groups and collaborating with companies as well as recognising innovative training and outreach efforts, and ensuring that data is acquired and stored in a way that allows it to be shared with other users.

As the visibility of Heritage Science increases, new user communities may arise, and significant government spending departments such as defence, healthcare, transport, and international development may start showing interest in Heritage Science. E-RIHS needs to be ready to respond to these changes, as well as to evolving international legislation and best practices in open data, open science, and intellectual property by updating policies frequently.

Heritage Science needs to seek out new developments in other areas of science, technology, and industry that could have applications in Heritage Science. Similarly, the Heritage Science community needs to work with industry to exploit developments made in Heritage Science for maximum impact.

The broad range of technologies, datatypes, and manufacturers found in Heritage Science makes open and FAIR data particularly challenging. E-RIHS can guide the Heritage Science community in developing a shared understanding of open data, which could contribute significantly to broader areas of science.

Table of contents

List of figures and tables	5
Abbreviations	6
Technical description	10
1. <i>Objectives</i>	10
2. <i>Innovation</i>	10
2.1 Development of an E-RIHS Innovation Strategy	10
2.2 The Heritage Science Innovation Ecosystem	11
2.3 Interactions of Heritage Science with other disciplines	12
2.4 Conclusions	13
2.5 Recommendations	13
2.5 IPERION HS response to recommendations	14
3. <i>Exploitation</i>	14
3.1 E-RIHS as an Innovation Ecosystem	14
3.2 What is it there to exploit and how can this be done?	16
3.3 Actions towards exploitation	17
3.4 Proposals.	18
4. <i>Interoperability</i>	18
4.1 Data in Heritage Science	18
4.2 The IPERION-HS Data Management Plan (DMP)	20
4.2 The IPERION-HS Interoperability Modelling Process	21
4.3 Selecting and Developing Tools	23
4.4 Developed General Shared Models	26
4.5 Developed Detailed Models	28
4.6 Interoperability Summary	30
Conclusions	33
References	34

List of Figures and Tables

Figures

Figure 1: Heritage Science Innovation Ecosystem taken from IPERION CH D9.2 Innovation Report (2018)

Figure 2: E-RIHS Innovation in Research, Training and Outreach

Figure 3: This simplified diagram represents the range of generic metadata models currently being considered and how they can be connected to each other.

Figure 4: This simplified diagram represents a very generic model of a piece of technical equipment.

Figure 5: A screenshot of the landing page for the Dynamic Modeller diagram tool displaying the default diagram which documents what the tool can do, and the text inputs used to create it.

Figure 6: Screenshot of Access-DS, displaying data entry for an E-RIHS access service

Table

Table 1 : Details and links for the initial draft shared models and JSON Schema that have been created within T6.3.

Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
API	Application Programming Interface, a way for two or more computer programs to communicate with each other. It is a type of software interface, offering a service to other pieces of software (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/API)
ARCHLAB	Access to archives
BALaT	“Belgium's art history in a single click, more than 750.000 downloadable photos”. http://balat.kikirpa.be/
BIM	Building Information Modelling
CIDOC	ICOM International Committee for Documentation (https://cidoc.mini.icom.museum/)
CIDOC CRM	The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) is a standard ontology developed for the Heritage domain. (https://www.cidoc-crm.org/)
CO	Coordination Office
Data	“In the pursuit of knowledge, data ... is a collection of discrete units of information in a conceptual model that in their most basic forms convey quantity, quality, fact, statistics, or other basic units of meaning.” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data)
DMP	Data Management Plan - For IPERION HS, the Data Management Plan (DMP) documents the agreed data management procedures and protocols used ... to organise, preserve and share data produced during the IPERION HS project. (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4541266)
EC	European Commission
ERIC	“The European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) is a specific legal form that facilitates the establishment and operation of Research Infrastructures with European interest.” - https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/eric_en
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science http://www.e-rihs.eu
E-RIHS IP	Horizon Europe - European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science Implementation Phase project, https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079148
E-RIHS PP	Horizon Europe - European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science Preparatory Phase project, https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/739503
E-RIHS.be	The Belgium national hub or E-RIHS.
EU H2020	“Horizon 2020 was the EU's research and innovation funding programme from 2014-2020 with a budget of nearly €80 billion.” (https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-2020_en)
FAIR	Provide guidelines related to improving the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital resources (https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/)
FIXLAB	Access to fixed research facilities
FTIR	Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fourier-transform_infrared_spectroscopy)
GC-MS	Gas Chromatography - Mass Spectrometry (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gas_chromatography%E2%80%93mass_spectrometry)
GitHub	An open, online software repository and development platform. (https://github.com)

HESCIDA	Heritage Science Data Archive, an infrastructure project of E-RIHS.be (2019 - 2023) with the aim of developing a national DIGILAB repository. The project is led by KIK/IRPA and funded by the Belgian Science Policy Office (http://hescida.kikirpa.be)
HS	“Heritage Science is the interdisciplinary domain of scientific study of cultural or natural heritage.” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Heritage_science)
Interoperability	Data interoperability in a broader sense means that data in diverse formats and from different locations or provenance can be unified, integrated or used together. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Interoperability , see also https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/)
IP	Intellectual Property
IPRMP	Intellectual Property Rights Management Plan
IPERION CH	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure on Cultural Heritage
IPERION HS	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science, EU funded H2020 project (https://www.iperionhs.eu)
IRUG	Infrared & Raman Users Group (http://www.irug.org)
IUPAC	International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry: a federation of National Adhering Organizations working for the advancement of the chemical sciences, especially by developing nomenclature and terminology
JavaScript	“JavaScript ... often abbreviated JS, is a programming language that is one of the core technologies of the World Wide Web ...” https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/JavaScript
JCAMP-DX	An open, human readable file format for data exchange (DX) in chemistry, originally developed by the Joint Committee on Atomic and Molecular Physical Data (JCAMP). IUPAC took over the responsibility of maintaining and extending the JCAMP-DX standards from JCAMP in 1995. (https://iupac.org/what-we-do/digital-standards/jcamp-dx)
JSON	JSON (which stands for JavaScript Object Notation) is an open standard file format developed for the exchange of digital data. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/JSON)
JSON Schema	JSON Schema is a vocabulary that allows you to annotate and validate JSON documents. JSON Schema is a vocabulary that allows one to define, annotate and validate JSON documents.
KIK/IRPA	Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage in Brussels, Belgium (Dutch: Koninklijk Instituut voor het Kunstpatrimonium; French: Institut royale du Patrimoine artistique; https://www.kikirpa.be)
M11	Milestone 11 from the IPERION-HS project - Padfield, Joseph, Fremont, Wim, Schmidle, Wolfgang, & Sotiropoulou, Sophia. (2022). Interim report on documentation of instrument parameters and analysis protocols across access platforms, and metadata requirements (1.2). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7101169
Metadata	“Metadata is data that provides information about other data, but not the content of the data, such as the text of a message or the image itself.” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Metadata)
MOLAB	Access to mobile research facilities
MFT	Microfading Testing (MFT) is an analytical technique used to determine an object’s light sensitivity. It is a method for assessing the vulnerability of individual museum objects to light-fading, including those for which the identity of the colourant is unknown.

MIT licence	“The MIT Licence is a permissive free software licence originating at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MIT_License) - https://choosealicense.com/licenses/mit/
Ontology	“In computer science and information science, an ontology encompasses a representation, formal naming, and definition of the categories, properties, and relations between the concepts, data, and entities that substantiate one, many, or all domains of discourse. “ (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ontology_(information_science)) - For examples see section 7.
Open Access	“Open access (OA) is a set of principles and a range of practices through which research outputs are distributed online, free of access charges or other barriers.” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_access)
Open Data	Fully “Open data is data that is openly accessible, exploitable, editable and shared by anyone for any purpose, even commercially. Open data is licensed under an open licence.” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_data)
ORCID	ORCID provides persistent digital identifiers (an ORCID iD) to researchers. (https://orcid.org/)
PARTHENOS	“Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies” http://www.parthenos-project.eu , which was funded by European Commission under the “H2020 – EU.1.4.1.1. – Developing new world-class research infrastructures”.
PID	Persistent Identifiers
Raman (Spectroscopy)	“... is a spectroscopic technique typically used to determine vibrational modes of molecules” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Raman_spectroscopy)
RDF	Resource Description Framework (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Resource_Description_Framework)
RI(s)	Research Infrastructure(s)
Semantic	Semantics “is the study of reference, meaning, or truth. “ (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Semantics) - In relation to this work Semantic Data can be described as data that has been described and categorised in relation to a formal ontology.
SSHOC	The Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud, EU funded H2020 project (https://www.sshopencloud.eu/)
SSHOCro	“The SSHOC Reference Ontology proposes an ontological model and RDF Schema to be used as a top-level ontology for organizing knowledge and information found distributed across various primary sources of information...” (https://isl.ics.forth.gr/SSHOCro/)
T6.3	Task 6.3 “Interoperability of instrumentation and digital documentation”, from Work-package 6 of the IPERION HS EU funded H2020 project.
TNA	Transnational Access, for more information see: https://www.iperionhs.eu/tag/tna/
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VJSF	Vuetify JSON Schema Forms: an open source library for generating webforms based on the JSON schema standard, based on the Vue and Vuetify frameworks (source code: https://github.com/koumoul-dev/vuetify-jsonschema-form , documentation: https://koumoul-dev.github.io/vuetify-jsonschema-form/latest)

Vocabulary	“Controlled vocabularies provide a way to organize knowledge for subsequent retrieval ... ” they “ ...mandate the use of predefined, authorised terms ... ” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Controlled_vocabulary) - such as the Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat) or even extracts from Wikidata (https://www.wikidata.org).
Zenodo	Zenodo is an open, free, catch-all data repository supported by CERN (https://home.cern), OpenAire (https://www.openaire.eu) and the EU Horizon 2020 Programme (https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020) – For more details see: https://zenodo.org .

Technical description

1. Objectives

E-RIHS is an innovative concept that offers unique and interdisciplinary solutions to the scientific and technical challenges in Heritage Science (HS). It provides state-of-the-art equipment and facilities, top-level expertise, data, archives, and collections. E-RIHS promotes a culture of innovation all across the spectrum of its research activities and maximizes the impact of HS research on scientific knowledge, technological know-how, and socio-economic growth based on the sustainable use of cultural heritage. It is expected that E-RIHS activities will provide further impacts benefiting the scientific community, sector operators, and the public at large.

The purpose of this Deliverable is to report on strategies aimed at maximising the socio-economic impact of IPERION HS and E-RIHS ERIC. We report on work that has examined opportunities for innovation, interoperability of instruments and data, and exploitation and engagement with industry.

This Deliverable builds on and extends previous Deliverables and Milestones of IPERION HS especially D6.1 *Data Management Plan for IPERION HS*, D6.2 *Exploitation Plan*, the *Interim report on Innovation* and Milestone 11, the *Interim report on documentation of instrument parameters and analysis protocols across access platforms, and metadata requirements*.

It addresses the following objectives of WP6 (Innovation and Exploitation):

- To formulate an innovation strategy to impact industry and promote its clustering with the RI in focus, promoting their involvement beyond technology development, thus opening the possibilities for future public-private partnerships.
- To improve the interoperability by investigating and comparing protocols, instrument parameters and practices for documenting data, and by defining the project Data Management Plan.
- To exploit all aspects of innovation achieved within IPERION HS and its preceding projects in the future E-RIHS by mapping key achievements and diverse expertise across the partnership, identifying research and application areas that require further development and by engaging the user community in the enhancement of access services.

2. Innovation

2.1 Development of an E-RIHS Innovation Strategy

IPERION HS commissioned a UK-based company called Qi3¹ to produce an independent report on Innovation Strategy for E-RIHS. Qi3 is a consultancy focussed on providing business advice to technology companies as well as research and governmental organisations and has successfully carried out similar work for previous projects.

¹ <https://www.qi3.co.uk/>

“Innovation” has intentionally been defined broadly, and includes innovation associated with knowledge exchange, training, technology and innovation developed through the research infrastructure facilities. The interactions between different aspects of innovation are summarised in Figure 1.

Qi3’s research was carried out in the first three months of 2021. They analysed documents from previous projects, especially IPERION CH and E-RIHS PP and carried out interviews with 12 members of IPERION HS, each bringing a different national perspective. The interviews were carried out remotely due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic. The contributors were actively involved in innovation, with a good understanding of the national situation and representing large and small countries from across Europe. The report was presented at the First Annual Meeting of IPERION HS on 22 April 2021; this Deliverable summarises the report.

Figure 1: Heritage Science Innovation Ecosystem from IPERION CH D9.2 Innovation Report (2018)

2.2 The Heritage Science Innovation Ecosystem

The report showed that many of the interactions between different players in Heritage Science shown in Figure 1 are uni-directional. This suggests that there is an opportunity for more discussion and involvement from stakeholders.

The meaning of the term “Heritage Science” is developing and it means different things to practitioners and to stakeholders in industry and in heritage organisations. Heritage Science needs to be seen to be broader than merely addressing the technical challenges of conservation. We need

to be able to explain to stakeholders why Heritage Science matters to them, and include the broad impacts on society as well as the generation of new knowledge. We also need to communicate a message to industry that Heritage Science is not just about the past; it is relevant to new building development now, especially in the changing climate.

Heritage Science can offer a complex but wide range of benefits. It is important to recognise and account for different types of value, including financial, human, public benefit as well as academic impact. It is important to communicate the intended impact at the start of a project and to involve stakeholders and the public in discussions about the co-creation of projects and their value.

The whole range of stakeholders should be considered and should include the tourism industry, heritage services, the built environment, media, entertainment, communities and mental wellbeing services. Engaging with the public and stakeholders openly throughout the development of a project will maximise the opportunities for impact and for successful deployment of innovation into other sectors.

2.3 Interactions of Heritage Science with other disciplines

Heritage Science and the Past

There is a well-established community of archaeologists, conservators, equipment manufacturers, insurers, and other service companies. Their customers include conservators, heritage institutions, heritage tourism, as well as the construction and media sectors. These customers constitute a diverse group with often diverse requirements.

Heritage Science and the Present

Heritage Science actively engages with the Built Environment community. This was identified as a New User Community that IPERON HS should engage with in task T7.4. For example, archaeology is an important aspect of new building developments. However, while there are regulations to protect heritage, these need to be enforced with flexibility and creativity to allow heritage assets to be sympathetically protected or repurposed as appropriate. A number of sectors are involved in these complex decisions, but they typically do not benefit from input from heritage scientists. It is important to demonstrate the value of Heritage Science in these contexts, including economic, wellbeing, cultural, sustainability and other values.

The increasing use of Building Information Modelling (BIM) may offer an opportunity for scientists trained in heritage to improve efficiency of construction and maintenance in a sympathetic way. BIM may create large datasets which benefit from the expertise of data scientists and Heritage Science may be well placed to offer this, for example in the context of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data protocols as described in sections 4.1 and 4.2. There is a need for training in this rapidly developing area to which heritage scientists may be able to contribute.

Interactions between Heritage Science and the media sector are relatively weak. Discussions between Qi3 and media organisations showed that they are typically unaware of Heritage Science but have complex needs around conservation for example of film, costumes and stage sets. Digital degradation in the form of obsolescence is as much a problem as physical degradation. Furthermore, heritage offers a source of creative material for the media sector which may not be fully exploited.

Heritage Science and the Future

The Qi3 report foresees new interactions between Heritage Science and industries that have had minimal previous engagement with heritage, such as wellbeing and mental health. Studies have shown that access to heritage sites can improve people's mental health and wellbeing, and this was highlighted during COVID-19 lockdowns and travel restrictions.

There are a number of national and international studies, listed in Qi3's report, addressing the links between Heritage Science and climate change. Heritage Science has a significant role in mitigating the impact of climate change on heritage assets, reducing the impact of heritage buildings on climate change and identifying and learning from historic adaptations to climate change.

2.4 Conclusions

The main conclusions of the report were that there is little comprehensive data on the Heritage Science innovation ecosystem and that the barriers that exist to improving our understanding are lack of resources, fragmentation of the Heritage Science ecosystem and a lack of understanding of all parties that are engaged in Heritage Science.

The report identifies "islands of excellence" in Heritage Science innovation across Europe but they are disparate and not connected. There are few national strategies and no international strategies. Connections between Heritage Science and some sectors such as built environment are relatively strong, but those with others such as media and wellbeing are weak.

2.5 Recommendations

The report made the following nine recommendations:

- The Framework identified by T6.1 for the Heritage Science Ecosystem, its constituent vectors for innovation, and participant sectors should be used to guide the development of innovation programmes as IPERION HS develops and informs the E-RIHS programme.
- IPERION HS should explore contacts with researchers in the humanities and social sciences who are evaluating the potential value of Heritage to Mental Health, Wellbeing, Community and Rehabilitation of Veterans to ensure that they are welcome as the Heritage Science Ecosystem develops into the E-RIHS programme.
- Most collaborations between Heritage Science and other sectors are built on personal relationships of researchers (Source: Qi3 Academic Survey on Industry Engagement - SEAHA and Wider Supervisors – 2018011501). It is essential that the Heritage Science ecosystem becomes a dynamic community of researchers and practitioners interacting regularly with each other form a creative mesh of innovative activities.
- To achieve this, IPERION HS should draft an "Ecosystem Innovation Engagement Programme" of activities for implementation in the E-RIHS programme that regularly brings people together in this dynamic environment.
- The "Ecosystem Innovation Engagement Programme" suggested above for E-RIHS should be planned by IPERION HS with European and Country scales in mind. It is important to for the European scale to provide structure, exemplars of good practice, and development of a Europe wide Heritage Science community. In parallel, it is important for the Country scale to be able to draw upon the European structures and exemplars to develop dynamic local Heritage Science communities.

- The Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage and Global Change (JPI CH) - Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda 2020 (SRIA 2020) states that JPI CH and E-RIHS represent highly complementary projects for the structuring of the cultural heritage research community, and that E-RIHS will greatly facilitate the implementation of the JPI CH's SRIA 2020. IPERION HS should establish close innovation links with JPI CH to plan how it and E-RIHS can work together to support the implementation of the JPI CH's SRIA 2020.
- IPERION HS should review all potential funding sources which have a remit to support Europe's innovation infrastructure and activities with the objective of finding the resources to fund the proposed E-RIHS "Ecosystem Innovation Engagement Programme". 2.5 IPERION HS response to recommendations

The Qi3 report was insightful and highlighted strengths and weaknesses in European Heritage Science innovation that will be developed through IPERION HS and related projects.

- The report produced by Qi3 will be used to help develop the innovation programmes in E-RIHS ERIC.
- Contacts with researchers in social sciences and humanities have been established in T7.3, which has included talks, webinars and further engagement as detailed in D7.2 "Detailed engagement plan for new users' communities". Contacts with researchers in mental health and wellbeing and the rehabilitation of veterans will be established and developed, for example through #HSAcademy. There is potential for connections between ARCHLAB and wellbeing in terms of allowing more people to experience art digitally. Further links exist between indoor pollution causing damage to health and heritage.
- Task 7.2 is developing a community of researchers through the #HSAcademy while T7.1 is addressing this recommendation through Doctoral Summer Schools and Training Camps.
- The Ecosystem Innovation Engagement Programme is being developed in collaboration with the other engagement activities of IPERION HS including those in WP7 and WP8 and, importantly, the Advisory Board for Regional Development Strategies (RDSAB) being established in T6.2.
- Members of IPERION HS have submitted proposals for JPI CH calls and will engage in preparation of future collaborative proposals.
- Funding opportunities are continually reviewed and proposals were submitted to the call highlighted in the recommendation. For example, a proposal led by the Fondation des Sciences du Patrimoine in France was submitted in October 2021 in the framework of the HORIZON-CL2-2021-HERITAGE-02 call, titled "Alliance for Research on Cultural Heritage in Europe" (ARCHE; Proposal ID 101060054) including 30 organizations, some of which are IPERION HS partners. This coordination network started its activity in September 2022 aiming at engaging cultural heritage actors in the co-design of Research and Innovation strategies and roadmaps.

3. Exploitation

3.1 E-RIHS as an Innovation Ecosystem

E-RIHS is an interdisciplinary partnership that encourages and facilitates innovation through different types of collaborations and strategic partnerships. It promotes a culture of innovation in

the spectrum of its research activities, access services, unique training activities, and management level, exploring new models for maximizing the impact of Heritage Science research on scientific knowledge, technological know-how, and socio-economic growth based on the sustainable use of cultural heritage.

It offers access to large-scale and medium-scale analytical facilities (FIXLAB), advanced mobile analytical instrumentation (MOLAB), and scientific datasets archived in knowledge repositories of prestigious European museums, galleries, and research institutions (ARCHLAB). In addition, it combines these services with unique expertise in designing or optimizing sophisticated scientific investigations and proper approaches for analysis and interpretation, specific to the targeted object or material, revealing their complex microstructure and chemical composition.

IPERION HS and the broader E-RIHS family of EC-supported projects have already developed significant innovations, including research-based tools, heritage-led methodologies, novel and efficient modes of access, knowledge spillover-technology transfer, and open data sharing and e-infrastructures that ensure sustainable, open digital archives.

The project is expected to have direct impacts on the quality and efficiency of scientific output in Heritage Science, benefitting the scientific community, sector operators, and the public at large. Europeans and public services will benefit from better access to non-technical knowledge, improved awareness and increased understanding of artistic and cultural assets, and enhanced access of citizens to culture, strengthening its message to society and generating positive impact on cultural tourism.

E-RIHS seeks to provide a model for other RIs seeking to exchange best practices and take advantage of innovations deriving from other scientific fields. As an open and collaborative platform, E-RIHS is poised to lead the way in the field of Heritage Science and beyond, with the potential for non-economic, non-technological, and social innovations, some of which are summarised in Figure 2.

E-RIHS: Innovation in Research, Training and Outreach

The MOLAB concept, introduced in 2003, was a highly innovative approach satisfying the needs of heritage researchers, who needed to make use of advanced diagnostic methods but were not in a position to move objects and not allowed to collect samples.

Now, IPERION HS offers MOLAB TNA with over 20 mobile instruments developed over the years.

Image © IPERION CH MOLAB Project

Through collaborative work in the IPERION CH project (WP6, JRA1: Innovative instruments and methods for integrated approaches to CH analysis and diagnostics), researchers at AGLAE, together with colleagues at BNC, IPANEMA and SOLEIL developed a versatile 3D positioner which enables accurate and reliable elemental mapping of non-flat surfaces of heritage objects.

T. Calligaro et al. "A new 3D positioner for the analytical mapping of non-flat objects under accelerator beams". *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B*: 467 (2020), pp. 65–72.

Methods in Physics Research Section B: 467 (2020), pp. 65–72.

The E-RIHS community has established a series of Doctoral Summer Schools, which are addressed to young PhD and post-doctoral researchers, the future users of E-RIHS facilities.

Two Doctoral Summer schools and two training camps were held as part of IPERION HS.

IPERION HS and E-RIHS have initiated a series of monthly webinars, which constitute a key source of state-of-the-art information on HS research, facilities, policy and impact. The series contributes to the development of a vibrant HS community and is intended for anyone involved in interdisciplinary heritage research.

Figure 2: E-RIHS Innovation in Research, Training and Outreach

3.2 What is it there to exploit and how can this be done?

The E-RIHS ecosystem produces a variety of innovative products with great potential for exploitation, yet there are few examples of successful commercialization. This suggests the existence of gaps preventing exploitation and commercialization of innovation. To address this, we need to define what is worth exploiting, identify potential products, and understand how innovative instruments, methods, or approaches can be exploited. It is also essential to identify the potential markets for the product, the expected benefits, and the value chain and profit. Moreover, it is important to identify who should undertake the effort of exploitation and what resources and key partnerships are required. Finally, it is essential to identify potential obstacles and inhibitors to the exploitation process.

The four common pathways for exploiting innovations deriving from E-RIHS are licensing agreements, establishing new companies, creating joint ventures, and outright sale of innovations. The most suitable pathway will depend upon several factors, including intellectual property (IP) rights, market size, and resources needed. Technology transfer and exploitation experts will advise

the involved parties on the optimal exploitation route, taking into consideration the unique characteristics of each individual case. The final decisions about the exploitation route will have to be made by the involved parties and their organizations.

3.3 Actions towards exploitation

IPERION HS has achieved major advancements in instrumentation and technologies, measurement methodologies and protocols, documentation tools, and data management procedures, as evidenced by the catalogue of services available on its website. The organization's innovations can be classified into four main types which are continually being evaluated and evolved, particularly through co-creation with users:

- new and adapted instrumentation
- new methodologies
- knowledge transfer
- user facilitation/new services/data support and recording.

The main drivers of the science strategy are to enhance knowledge of heritage, preserve heritage, and develop new capabilities for Heritage Science. This necessitates using advanced scientific techniques and interdisciplinary collaboration and opens up opportunities for exploitation of these developments.

Engaging user communities is critical. Users are active collaborators in the research, and their expertise should be nurtured. In an innovation ecosystem like IPERION HS, users can become providers, leading to co-creation of new research areas. To evaluate how users perceive the quality and impact of access and identify potential needs for enhancing access services, a questionnaire was distributed through National Coordinators to users of National RIs based in different member states.

To monitor innovation effectively, E-RIHS must establish appropriate mechanisms for fostering the generation of ideas and monitoring the generation and growth of innovation from its early stages. It is essential to set up an internal mechanism that will liaise with other mechanisms and tools to identify and assess the potential of existing or new ideas and tools, identifying emerging opportunities for innovation.

There is a need for a well-defined and balanced IP support system that is adjustable to different types of innovations and promotes creativity and innovation. We recommend developing an IPR Management Plan (IPRMP) in E-RIHS ERIC, which will involve assessing and understanding the value of technological and instrumental assets, evaluating and adopting an IPRMP coherent with the distributed nature and business plan of E-RIHS, and developing a dynamic strategy for implementation that foresees future IP developments within the RI. It is important that innovations that require IP protection, and decisions concerning IP rights, ownership, and exploitation potentials of the developed IP are discussed early in the project, especially when several actors are involved in the development of an innovation.

3.4 Proposals.

There is a need for a well-defined plan to efficiently exploit and commercialize innovation in the field of Heritage Science. Despite numerous research achievements, there is a disproportionately small number of innovative findings that are subsequently successfully exploited by E-RIHS partners. To bridge this exploitation and innovation gap, we propose several actions:

- It is necessary to continue to train researchers to develop the necessary skills and competencies to understand and determine the innovation potential of their work. Specialized training, particularly for young researchers, is essential for identifying opportunities and developing a plan for exploitation.
- We recommend the establishment of a Central Liaison Office (CLO) for Innovation. This office will liaise with local technology transfer offices (TTO) in participating organizations to assess the innovation produced. The CLO will also provide customized assistance and consultancy services to researchers in cases of exploitable innovation outcomes, facilitate contacts with investors and venture capital firms, and organize special “Innovation events.”
- We recommend the creation of an Innovation Radar, a tool that will detect emerging opportunities in terms of financing innovation, collaboration opportunities, funding schemes, and encouraging synergies between stakeholders. The Innovation Radar will scan not only the E-RIHS ecosystem but a much broader range of relevant ideas and technologies in different sectors, such as medical diagnostic technologies, automotive and aerospace, construction and buildings sector, and forensics and environment.
- E-RIHS will need to improve the mutual cooperation between RIs and industry. In the case of HS, industry is considered in its broadest sense, including commercial companies from the cultural and creative sectors as well as museums, galleries, archives and private companies of conservators and restorers, some of which are small enterprises and hard to engage with.

4. Interoperability

4.1 Data in Heritage Science

Interoperability is crucial in enabling data to be shared and used across different systems and platforms. A key process for achieving interoperability is through the mapping of metadata to domain standard ontologies and controlled vocabularies. This can ensure that the metadata is classified, defined, and linked together in a standard way, allowing services to automatically aggregate and combine data from multiple sources and promote the discovery of raw data and other related research resources. In relation to the field of Heritage Science (HS) the concept of levels of interoperability, from unrelated data to some form of full semantic interoperability has been discussed within T6.3. This work was intended to explore the potential complexity of the problem, identify some of the key aspects of interoperability for research data and establish how they might be put into practice. These discussions determined that the development of a standardised set of these levels, like the examples reported in the interim milestone report (M11) for this task², should be considered as aspirational rather than current practice, as further work, development, and training is still required before informed consensus could be reached. It was also

² See section 3.1 of: Padfield, Joseph, Fremont, Wim, Schmidle, Wolfgang, & Sotiropoulou, Sophia. (2022). Interim report on documentation of instrument parameters and analysis protocols across access platforms, and metadata requirements (1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7101169>

agreed that beginning the work by considering full semantic interoperability would be very complex for non-specialists and would minimise participation and understanding among the wider variety of researchers within the E-RIHS community. Therefore, the main body of work in T6.3 has concentrated a more accessible, bottom-up approach, to identify what key metadata could, practically, be made interoperable, to maximize its exploitability, and how that data needs to be managed as a key part of ensuring that HS data can be *FAIR* (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable)³.

This work concentrated on four main objectives. Firstly, the development of an overall data management plan for IPERION-HS, identifying some of the key aspects of the HS data life cycle. Secondly, exploring and testing practical approaches to interoperability, based on existing expertise. Thirdly, developing an agreed strategy or framework for defining and documenting the metadata required to achieve acceptable levels of interoperability. And finally, identifying and developing appropriate generic tools and procedures to help researchers gather the identified metadata and document their own instrument parameters, analysis protocols, and research data. The aim has been to break up the data life cycle of HS research into discrete shared and re-usable parts, such as projects, people, examinations, equipment, etc.⁴ and agree a common general approach to linking and modelling the metadata required to usefully document each of these parts.

Metadata modelling is an essential aspect of achieving interoperability, as it involves defining the rules and relationships relevant to the construction of a specific model of knowledge. Within T6.3, the focus has been on capturing the language and relationships used by domain experts to describe their own areas of expertise. The metadata models considered, summarised in Figure , represent a range of generic, reusable, shared concepts that link together to form the overall data life cycle. Along with a smaller selection of detailed models capturing the full complexity of the metadata required to describe specific experiments/technical examinations. These models are intended to act as a guide or template for how other HS work can be consistently modelled, with the aim of ensuring that data gathered in relation to specific techniques across different institutions and countries can follow the same core, interoperable foundations.

Developing full models for all these concepts and all the techniques listed in the current IPERION HS catalogue of services⁵ is obviously beyond the scope of this individual task, but the work begun in this task can be developed and implemented more widely going forward.

³ For more details of the Fair principles see: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

⁴ For an example see: <https://national-gallery.github.io/dynamic-modelling?url=https://raw.githubusercontent.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/main/Model%20Relationships/Models%20-%20V0.5.tsv>

⁵ <https://www.iperionhs.eu/catalogue-of-services/>

Figure 3: This simplified diagram⁶ represents the range of generic metadata models currently being considered and how they can be connected to each other.

4.2 The IPERION-HS Data Management Plan (DMP)

The DMP⁷ is a set of data management procedures and protocols created for IPERION HS to help organize, preserve, and share HS data. It provides guidance to ensure that all data and processes are as open and FAIR as possible while remaining as closed as necessary. The DMP also describes what is meant by HS data, publishing data, and how the FAIR principles relate to HS data.

The DMP also practically documents how to manage the data created and/or used during each access to IPERION HS facilities or during each piece of work within the project. It summarises how

⁶ This simplified model is based on version 0.5 of the E-RIHS interoperability model diagram: see <https://national-gallery.github.io/dynamic-modelling/?url=https://raw.githubusercontent.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/main/Model%20Relationships/Models%20-%20V0.5.tsv>

⁷ Padfield, Joseph. (2021). D6.1 Data Management Plan for IPERION HS (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788560>

the collections of data, and its relevant documentation can be packaged up and published in an open data repository. In addition, the DMP states that the agreed default open data repository for IPERION HS is Zenodo⁸, where published datasets can be gathered in a dedicated "community" for IPERION HS.⁹

To publish data through Zenodo or equivalent data repository, the DMP recommends gathering all the required data and metadata, procedural documents/method statements, and equipment details together. Researchers then need to confirm all the required publication licenses for the gathered data, complete any reports, publications or deliverables, and ensure all relevant data, descriptions, and references are in an agreed format. Finally, researchers need to upload their prepared package of data and files to their chosen data repository and register the details of the published data with the IPERION HS Coordination Office if they have not already done so via Zenodo.

Overall, the DMP is intended to help researchers effectively manage and share HS data by providing practical guidelines and recommendations for data management, publishing, and registration.

In addition to producing the actual project DMP this task has also developed a series of data life cycle workflow diagrams to make it easier to follow the various steps or stages discussed in the DMP. These diagrams have been published on GitHub¹⁰ with, at the time of writing, the latest full version being version 1.2.¹¹

The IPERION HS DMP is now being further developed, within E-RIHS IP, to become the first version of the E-RIHS (ERIC) DMP.

4.2 The IPERION-HS Interoperability Modelling Process

Within E-RIHS, many different specialists and researchers, from many different countries will be involved in documenting their research work digitally. This documentation needs to be interoperable, easy to edit and share, and ideally work well within multiple different documentation systems. To facilitate this, T6.3 has followed a practical approach to identifying the key entities (Services, Projects, Equipment, etc.) in HS research and the groups or models of metadata fields required to document them. Within T6.3 the more common of these metadata models were defined and agreed upon by the group of researchers directly participating in the Task, but more specific models, such as those for particular analytical techniques or equipment, were defined in collaboration with domain experts in the relevant fields. All the models have been saved in an open format, like simple text files, making it easy to use and develop them in the future.

⁸ Zenodo is an open, free, catch-all data repository supported by CERN (<https://home.cern>), OpenAire (<https://www.openaire.eu>) and the EU Horizon 2020 Programme (<https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020>) – For more details see: <https://zenodo.org>.

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/871034/?page=1&size=20>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/tree/main/DMP>

¹¹ <https://national-gallery.github.io/dynamic-modelling/?url=https://raw.githubusercontent.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/main/DMP/IPERION-HS%20DMP%20Workflow%20V1.2.tsv>

To make the models even easier to understand and discuss, diagrams were created, see Figure . When finished or agreed versions of the models are completed, they are then being converted into a JSON schema document¹² and uploaded to the required E-RIHS model repository¹³.

Figure 4: This simplified diagram¹⁴ represents a very generic model of a piece of technical equipment.

Within T6.3, although not an initial priority, it has also been agreed that another useful step will be to map the gathered data, via the underlying schema documents, to standard domain ontologies to facilitate further interoperability and semantic searching. Therefore, the models were created with CIDOC CRM compatibility in mind¹⁵. Although there have not currently been any formal semantic mappings created within T6.3, this work has begun within the related E-RIHS IP project.

More generally, in addition to the CIDOC CRM, T6.3 has also made use of and been guided by other existing standards where appropriate. Among the other existing resources and ontologies that have already being used or considered within the work of T6.3: the *SSHOCro extension to the CIDOC CRM*,

¹² As described in section: Metadata Templates defined and visualised by JSON Schema

¹³ At this time all of the JSON schema documents are being stored on GitHub (<https://github.com/E-RIHS/schema>) – from here they can all then be referenced and or reused via a direct URL based on the following pattern: `e-rihs.github.io/schema/MODELNAME-vVERSIONNUMBER.schema.json`. For example: <https://e-rihs.io/schema/project-v0.4.schema.json>

¹⁴ This simplified model is based on version 0.2 of the generic equipment model diagram: see <https://national-gallery.github.io/dynamic-modelling/?url=https://raw.githubusercontent.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/main/Shared%20Models/Equipment%20Model%20-%20V0.2.tsv>

¹⁵ CIDOC CRM is a high-level ontology for the cultural heritage that is increasingly used as the basis for modelling HS data, for more information see <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/>

work from the ongoing HESCIDA project and the already finished PARTHENOS project, have help to inform how our models been developed.¹⁶

Future work¹⁷ will involve integrating the finished JSON schema documents into live data gathering systems¹⁸, linking or referencing data entered into related schemas together and then carrying out data validation tests with E-RIHS researchers.

4.3 Selecting and Developing Tools

Where possible, to support the sustainability and accessibility of the work carried out within T6.3, open-source tools and procedures have been selected or developed.

The Dynamic Modeller

A dynamic online modelling tool¹⁹ was created²⁰ to facilitate live, virtual, collaborative development of metadata models and their documentation (see Figure 5). The tool automatically generates flow diagrams from tab-separated data sets using a simple user interface split into two sections for the text and resultant model. The system was initially designed to facilitate modelling discussions during online meetings but was updated to allow users to copy and paste text²¹ directly from online collaborative spreadsheets, or reference external data files. Users can also make use of a range of predefined shapes and colours to enhance the generated models.²²

The tool and its documentation have been designed to make the models created in T6.3 and the process for creating them as FAIR as possible. Raw text/data can be shared in various formats, and models can also be easily shared as links and PNG or SVG images. The code for the system is published on GitHub²³ under the MIT licence²⁴ and is built using open and freely available software libraries²⁵. The system has also been uploaded to the data repository Zenodo²⁶ and published in the SSHOC Marketplace²⁷ to increase accessibility.

¹⁶ See section 7 of Padfield, Joseph, Fremont, Wim, Schmidle, Wolfgang, & Sotiropoulou, Sophia. (2022). Interim report on documentation of instrument parameters and analysis protocols across access platforms, and metadata requirements (1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7101169>

¹⁷ This work is continuing within the IPERION-HS project, but it is also being incorporated into the new Horizon Europe E-RIHS IP project (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079148>).

¹⁸ An example prototype system is also being developed within this task, see section: Access Documentation System (pilot)

¹⁹ The live version of this system can be found at: <https://national-gallery.github.io/dynamic-modelling/>

²⁰ The development of this tool was a collaborative effort spread across this and several other projects, including the EU Horizon 2020 funded SSHOC - Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (823782) (<https://sshopencloud.eu/>), along with work carried out to support the Linked.Art project (<https://linked.art/>).

²¹ Rows and columns copied from spreadsheets are automatically formatted as tab separated data when then they are pasted into other text-based systems.

²² A fourth tab separated value is used to indicate the required formatting - all the currently available options can be seen at: https://national-gallery.github.io/dynamic-modelling/?example=example_formats

²³ The source code is available on GitHub: <https://github.com/national-gallery/dynamic-modelling>

²⁴ See: <https://github.com/national-gallery/dynamic-modelling/blob/master/LICENCE>.

²⁵ The diagram is created using the open source JavaScript library Mermaid - "... diagramming and charting tool that renders Markdown-inspired text definitions to create and modify diagrams dynamically." - <https://mermaid-js.github.io>

²⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4724103>

²⁷ <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/ASSQXO>

Figure 5: A screenshot of the landing page for the Dynamic Modeller diagram tool²⁸, displaying the default diagram documenting what the tool can do, and the text inputs used to create it.

Metadata Templates defined and visualised by JSON Schema

JSON is an open standard file format developed for the exchange of digital data. Though designed to be a machine-readable text format, a JSON document is also human readable, but it is not really a format intended to be created directly by most (human) researchers. The types of information (e.g. strings, numbers, dates, etc.) expected within a specific JSON document can be defined using the JSON Schema vocabulary²⁹. This combination provides a strong, sustainable solution for capturing and storing complex HS data as the content and its structure can be stored in one open exchangeable document that can be opened and used by many other pieces of software. Another benefit is that the same structure can be used to create empty templates that describe the agreed fields and data types required to define a given project, object, experiment, etc.

To make the process even easier, a number of open-source software libraries exist that can translate a JSON Schema template automatically into a form embedded in a website, for data entry. These forms, when filled in, can then subsequently export the entered fields as JSON data. In-built form validation also guarantees that this data is compliant with the schema outlined in the template. These open-source software libraries can be included in a range of different existing or future systems, from data gathering prototypes, as planned within this task, to integrated digital documentation systems developed for different large or small institutions. Thus, providing an open

²⁸ <https://national-gallery.github.io/dynamic-modelling/>

²⁹ See <https://json-schema.org/>

sustainable solution that can be used collaboratively across the HS domain without requiring everyone to use a specific piece of documentation software.

Three different open-source libraries have been evaluated as possible solutions for developing this approach to using JSON Schema templates and visualising them as web forms: JSON Editor³⁰, VJSF³¹ and JSONForms³². Basic JSON Schema were correctly rendered as web forms with all three libraries, though each did offer some additional, but different, options to define further formatting. VJSF was selected for use within T6.3, as it was already being used within KIK/IRPA's Metahub³³, and a purpose-built Form Generator³⁴ was built using the tool to facilitate the writing, testing, and sharing JSON Schema definitions amongst the partners in this task.

Access Documentation System (pilot)

To elicit feedback on the models and JSON Schema that were developed and to demonstrate future possibilities to the research community, T6.3 initiated the development of a web application called Access-DS³⁵. The aim of this application is to showcase and facilitate the documentation of all aspects of an E-RIHS access project. Access-DS is primarily built on the codebase of Metahub, which is a documentation system for projects, samples, reports and analytical data that is currently under development at KIK/IRPA as part of the HESCIDA project, that also uses JSON Schema to model and harmonise metadata.

The Access-DS application is composed of three components: a database, an application programming interface (API), and a front-end graphical user interface (see figure 6). The data that needs to be collected is described by a set of JSON Schemas, which may undergo modifications over time. This type of dataset, the structure of which is defined by an external standard, is best stored in what is known as a document database³⁶. In Access-DS, a MongoDB³⁷ database is utilized for this purpose. The API functions as a machine-to-machine communication gateway that provides controlled access to the database. Access-DS employs a REST-compliant³⁸ API. The front-end is a user interface that is linked to the API, in which the JSONForms library is utilized to generate data gathering forms.

At the moment, a generic page for data entry has been implemented. In a first step, the submitter has to choose a type of data to enter. This loads the corresponding JSON Schema³⁹, which is displayed in the second step. If the entered data is valid, the user can store the dataset in the database. For some types of data and at certain TNA providers, there may already be existing

³⁰ JSON Editor source code: <https://github.com/json-editor/json-editor>, demo app: <https://json-editor.github.io/json-editor>

³¹ VJSF website: <https://koumoul-dev.github.io/vuetify-jjsonschema-form/latest/>, source code: <https://github.com/koumoul-dev/vuetify-jjsonschema-form>

³² JSONForms website: <https://jsonforms.io/>, demo application: <https://jsonforms-editor.netlify.app/>

³³ Metahub source code: <https://github.com/KIKIRPA/metahub>

³⁴ The IPERION-HS Form Generator is available on <https://bytes.kikirpa.be/form-generator/>, the (MIT licensed) source code is available on GitHub - <https://github.com/KIKIRPA/form-generator>

³⁵ The source code is available on GitHub: <https://github.com/E-RIHS/access-ds>;

³⁶ See: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Document-oriented_database

³⁷ See: <https://github.com/mongodb/mongo>

³⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Representational_state_transfer

³⁹ These are cached locally, but updated regularly from: <https://github.com/E-RIHS/schema>

documentation tools in use. To avoid researchers having to enter their data twice, existing systems could be connected to the Access-DS API, so that existing data can be re-used. For example, when a user is documenting a "Project" they can just select "Services" rather than having to re-enter all the required "Service" metadata.

The screenshot shows a web interface for creating a new service dataset. At the top, there is a header with the E-RIHS logo and navigation tabs for 'GENERIC RECORD ENTRY' and 'PROJECT WORKFLOW'. The main heading is 'New 'Service' dataset'. The form contains the following fields:

- Id:** ARCHLAB01
- Title*:** Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (37 / 100 characters)
- Service Summary*:** The archives are a unique and interdisciplinary resource for scientific, photographic and technical documentation of the cultural heritage of Belgium. It contains reports, must NOT have more than 300 characters (383 / 300 characters)
- Service Readiness Level:** 9 - Service proven in operational environment (production)
- Operating Languages:** A list with a '+' button to add more. The current list includes:
 - en - English
 - nl - Dutch
 - fr - French

Figure 6: Screenshot of Access-DS, displaying data entry for an E-RIHS access service

Generic data entry is the first use-case demonstration of the application. Further development on Access-DS is planned to run until the end of the IPERION-HS project and then be continued, going forward by the E-RIHS community. A second use-case will be added to demonstrate a possible project submission and peer review flow for requesting a TNA access. Also, a basic authentication (based on ORCID) and authorization will be added.

4.4 Developed General Shared Models

Handling and sharing data related to IPERION HS activities will require specific data models to be developed to ensure that all the appropriate metadata is recorded for specific techniques and procedures. However, there are several parts of the research data life cycle that can rely on common models, defining shared or reused data. For example, we should not need to redefine or record the metadata for the IPERION HS project for every access. The shared models will be used to generate JSON Schema to evaluate and optimise the models, and to facilitate future data entry. Details and links for some of the draft shared models and schema are given in Table 2. As noted before this work is ongoing within this project and planned to continue across future initiatives. Improved versions

of these models⁴⁰ and JSON Schema⁴¹ will be added to the GitHub repository as they are developed within T6.3.

Table 2 : Details and links for the initial draft shared models and JSON Schema that have been created within T6.3.

Model	Description	Model	Schema
Actor	An initial draft exploring the notion of actors, and then the needs to define persons and organisations.	0.1	
Dimension	An initial draft of how actual numerical values can be recorded to define the ranges, targets or settings required for pieces of analytical equipment.	0.1	
Equipment ⁴²	A specific piece of analytical or examination equipment with defined detectors, Model Numbers, Working distances etc.	0.2	
Examination	An initial draft relating to the examination of object or archives	0.1	
Measurement	An individual analytical measurement, with reference to relevance techniques, equipment, experimental conditions, etc.	0.1	
Object	A broad possible range of heritage collection objects, such as paintings, sculpture, books, archaeological stone, etc.	0.2	
Project	A project defines the concept of an access project in one of the E-RIHS access platforms	0.3	0.3
Service	A service represents the situation where access to a particular technique, using a specific piece or set up of equipment, following a defined, consistent series or processes or procedures is made available for researchers.	0.3	0.4
Support	An initial draft exploring the notion of entities that support services. (*) The support model is implemented as a subschema in the Services schema 0.4	0.2	*
Technique	A general analytical or examination technique used to study heritage collection objects or mock-ups,	0.3	

⁴⁰ <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/tree/main/Shared%20Models>

⁴¹ <https://github.com/E-RIHS/schema>

⁴² An example of this simple model can be seen Figure .

	materials, etc.- such as Raman, Reflectance Spectroscopy, GC-MS, etc.		
--	---	--	--

4.5 Developed Detailed Models

Reflectance Spectroscopy - Artificial Ageing

Reflectance Spectroscopy - Artificial Ageing has been selected as one of the use cases for testing the under development shared models, focusing on the sub-models developed to document analytical protocols and series of examinations and measurements with different methodologies involving a selection of techniques and supporting equipment. The objective is to identify a common general approach to modelling documentation schemes, to capture a realistic and useful level of metadata, but, with a degree of modularity to allow the specific core metadata to be defined by experts of each technique.

A parallel aim of this work was to achieve interoperability among laboratories involved in the IPERION HS Joint Research Activity 5.1 - Methodological and instrumental developments for preventive conservation, using multi-instrumental methodologies for a multi-dimensional analysis of change in the appearance and the structural stability of painted art objects. Interoperability is required to enable comparison and combination of data obtained at the partner laboratories using different equipment and protocols. In the IPERION HS JRA framework, Reflectance spectroscopy is used for the detection and monitoring of colour/chemical change of pigments under the effect of accelerated photo-ageing procedures and the acquired data will be, in addition, assessed comparatively with Microfading test (*MFT*) data also produced in the same task.

A common metadata structure with core metadata fields has been adopted and shared to be used for documenting the artificial ageing experiments and diffuse reflectance measurements (equipment specs, instrumental settings, and measurement conditions) applied for monitoring the change of colour on paint mock-ups and objects. The metadata schema is following the general approach developed in T6.3 and is aligned with the separate part-models (Object, Technique, Equipment, Measurement) that are interconnected to cover the complete data creation process according to a predefined a workflow and individual protocols of examination.

Up to now, exchange among partners on the metadata schema has been carried out using a spreadsheet file format⁴³, but the creation and update of the metadata templates in JSON format are planned.

Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy is an established analytical technique for the characterisation of a wide range of inorganic and organic materials in HS: pigments, dyes, polymers, mortars, salts, etc. In addition, Raman spectroscopy is listed in the IPERION HS catalogue of services⁵. Therefore, it was selected as an example to be worked out within this task.

A wide variety of instrumental set-ups and instrumental parameters exist: dispersive or transformation-based instruments, microscope-based and/or glass fibre probe-coupled systems,

⁴³ <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/tree/main/Technique/Reflectance Spectroscopy>

different laser wavelengths, etc. Knowledge of these parameters is of utmost importance when comparing spectra obtained with different systems, since these may have a major influence on the spectra.

The IRUG is a community that encourages the sharing of high-quality comparative reference spectral data in HS, both for FTIR and Raman spectroscopy. IRUG collects FTIR and Raman reference spectra for the study of works of art, architecture and archaeological materials, and offers their peer-reviewed database through their website⁴⁴ (open for all) and for download (to contributors only). IRUG uses an extended and standardised form of the open and human-readable *JCAMP-DX* format for documenting and sharing spectra.⁴⁵ IRUG has added a large number of labelled, data records and instructions to extensively document Raman and FTIR spectra of HS reference materials.

In the framework of HESCIDA, a JSON schema was made. This schema was heavily influenced by the IRUG metadata specifications. Conversion to/from their *JCAMP-DX* format should be straightforward and easy to automate. Some aspects from the IRUG specifications describe the sample and its origin, with a strong focus on reference materials and therefore not always usable to describe samples of heritage objects or for measurements performed directly on the objects. Detailed sample metadata was therefore not included and will become a linked resource; only the reference to a sample is captured in the Raman schema.

The generic Raman schema⁴⁶, as developed in the HESCIDA project has been posted on the GitHub E-RIHS HS-interoperability workspace. A derivative schema “*raman_invia785*”⁴⁷ was created as an example schema for a specific frequently used set-up at KIK/IRPA in which a number of metadata values are predefined (e.g. instrument: Renishaw InVia) and other metadata restricted to a selectable list of predefined values (e.g. a list with the objective lenses that are available on this system).

Museum environmental data

Museum environmental data, relating to factors such as temperature, relative humidity, light, and pollutants is essential for the preservation and care of cultural heritage. Monitoring it allows museums to understand the conditions experienced by collections and develop conservation strategies and inform decisions about resource allocation. Keeping a good record of this data also allows museums to study long term trends in their environmental conditions and track any effect on collections. Exporting and sharing museum environmental data is also an important part of the procedure of loaning collection works, with collections routinely requesting sets of data to demonstrate the conditions that are maintained within exhibitions spaces. However this process of sharing museum environmental data can be very varied. Data is provided in multiple formats, everything from images and spreadsheets to PDFs and text files. There is currently no standard way

⁴⁴ <http://irug.org/about-us/the-database>

⁴⁵ Beth A. Price, Boris Pretzel, Suzanne Quillen Lomax, Charles Davis, Janice H. Carlson. “Revised *JCAMP-DX* Spectral File Format for Submissions to the Infrared & Raman Users Group (IRUG) Spectral Database”, 2013. <http://irug.org/uploads/documentation/irug-jcamp-dx-revised-white-paper-text-only-with-2b-version-1-26-sept-2013.pdf>

⁴⁶ <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/blob/main/External%20Models/HESCIDA/raman.schema.json>

⁴⁷ https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/blob/main/External%20Models/HESCIDA/raman_invia785.schema.json

of exporting this type of data and the relevant metadata required to put it in context and allow museum staff to exploit it efficiently and consistently.

Standards, such as EODEM⁴⁸, are being developed to facilitate the transference of some aspects of loans collections data and any required environmental limits and ranges. However, this work does not yet extend to the actual environmental data itself or to any of the metadata related to the equipment and systems used to collect it. T6.3 has begun working on some example environmental data to demonstrate how the developed modelling approach can be extended to this type of data, considering the metadata required to describe the various types of environmental variables, data sensors and the locations in which they are installed. The initial model⁴⁹ based on abbreviated data, exported from the National Gallery⁵⁰, is quite complex, but it is anticipated that it will be possible to break it up into several related models and exploit some of the more generic, shared models already being developed, see section: 4.4 Developed General Shared Models.

Optical Microscopy

Optical microscopy is a key tool for studying a wide range of different heritage objects or samples, a common example being paint samples. These samples are regularly studied and imaged using Optical Microscopic equipment and the collection and sharing of related images and data has already been the focus of much work.⁵¹ Following the same procedures described before the process of taking, preparing, and imaging paint samples has been simplified into two initial models, one relating to the creation of the sample⁵² and the other relating to its subsequent examination with Optical Microscopy.⁵³ These initial models will continue to be developed within T6.3 and expected to act as the basis of related work, examining the management and recording of digital assets created with Optical Microscopy.⁵⁴

4.6 Interoperability Summary

The modelling approach explored within T6.3 and presented here is proving to be successful. It is continuing to be developed within IPERION-HS and is now also being directly exploited in E-RIHS IP. The more accessible approach of breaking the complex HS data life cycle into manageable chunks and combining clearer models and workflows has allowed a broader range of HS specialists to contribute and comment of the work. Connecting the work to the development of the E-RIHS community catalogue of services⁵⁵, by creating a new services model and new forms for providers to discuss, submit and define new and existing services has provided a clear example of the practical purpose of what is commonly seen as a more theoretical exercise. Moving beyond the direct

⁴⁸ Exhibition Object Data Exchange Model (<https://cidoc.mini.icom.museum/working-groups/documentation-standards/eodem-home/>)

⁴⁹ <https://national-gallery.github.io/dynamic-modelling/?url=https://raw.githubusercontent.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/main/Technique/Environmental%20Data/Environmental%20Data%20-%20Model%20-%20V0.1.tsv>

⁵⁰ <https://research.ng-london.org.uk/scientific/env/?start=2010-01-01&finish=2010-01-02&data=1&ids=116>

⁵¹ For example see: Marika Spring, & Joseph Padfield. (2018). IPERION-CH D.8.6 Two digital research resources available for open access on the web and one working resource. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5838339>

⁵² <https://national-gallery.github.io/dynamic-modelling/?url=https://raw.githubusercontent.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/main/Technique/Optical%20Microscopy/Paint%20Sampling%20Model%20-%20V0.1.tsv>

⁵³ <https://national-gallery.github.io/dynamic-modelling/?url=https://raw.githubusercontent.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/main/Technique/Optical%20Microscopy/Imaging%20Paint%20Sample%20Model%20-%20V0.1.tsv>

⁵⁴ This related work is being carried out within the National Gallery, as part of an internal Digital Documentation Project, but the relevant results of this work will also be integrated into T6.3 and subsequent work as appropriate.

⁵⁵ The current version of this can be seen at: <https://www.iperionhs.eu/catalogue-of-services/>

participants of IPERION-HS and E-RIHS IP discussions⁵⁶ have also begun exploring how this approach and the various models being created can be compared and harmonised with other HS related data models. The aim of these external discussions is to ensure that the data models being created for the E-RIHS community can represent the needs and best practices of the wider HS community and act as more standard central reference point for the development of improved interoperability for HS.

To summarise the work being carried out in relation to T6.3 the following recommended steps or points to consider have been put together for future interoperability modelling work:

1. Define the specific list of new entities (events, methods, and equipment, etc.) that need to be documented.
2. Compare the new list with existing models to minimize the duplicate of effort.
3. Contribute new use cases or issues to any of the relevant existing models⁵⁷.
4. Define a list of the key metadata fields required to describe the new entities or activities being modeled⁵⁸.
5. Convert the text-based description into a simple diagram to ensure all the relationships work well and meet the agreed requirements.
6. Where models or diagrams get more complex, if appropriate, break up the current entity or activity into smaller, simpler, linked entities or activities⁵⁹.
7. Record each stage of the development of models as different documented versions, for example “Model Name - V0.1.tsv”.
8. Save your documented versions in an open collaborative workspace,⁶⁰ where they can be cited and referenced.
9. Following existing examples, convert finished or agreed models into standardized JSON schema documents⁶¹ that can be used to automatically generate data gathering forms in different applications and systems.
10. Submit the finished JSON schema to be assessed before being included into the E-RIHS Schema repository.⁶²

⁵⁶ For example with the developers of more general documentation systems like <https://www.archesproject.org/arches-for-science/>

⁵⁷ This can be done by contributing to any live discussions or by submitting a new issue in GitHub (<https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/issues>).

⁵⁸ This has been done in the form of simple tab separated triples, such as Entity – has – Title, or as part of more complex spreadsheet-based templates.

⁵⁹ For example, an event could be broken up into different stages or a complex piece of equipment could be described as a combination of re-usable components.

⁶⁰ As noted, within this task, documented models have been saved on GitHub under: <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability>

⁶¹ See section: Metadata Templates defined and visualised by JSON Schema

⁶² <https://github.com/E-RIHS/schema> - at the time of writing the submission process is relatively straight forward, but a more complex editorial and peer-review process is envisaged as the process develops.

It is understood that although several of these steps can be carried out by less technical HS specialist, by referencing and developing similar existing models, it is anticipated that some form of new modelling or documentation support services may be required going forward.

Conclusions

Innovation, exploitation and interoperability are critical to the success of E-RIHS because they are key to ensuring that the impact of the project is maximised. There are opportunities to work with new user groups, to engage with companies and to ensure that innovation around training and outreach is recognised and celebrated.

International legislation and best practice around open and FAIR data, open science, and intellectual property is evolving and E-RIHS needs to respond to this. Policies in these areas will need to be live documents, frequently updated in response to the changing landscape.

New user communities will arise as the visibility of Heritage Science increases, meaning that the scope of Heritage Science increases and other disciplines become more aware of Heritage Science. Significant government spending departments such as defence, healthcare, transport and international development may start to gain interest in heritage and Heritage Science; E-RIHS needs to be ready to respond.

The interaction goes both ways; not only will Heritage Science contribute to an increasing range of disciplines, but Heritage Science also needs to actively learn from other areas of science, technology and industry. We need to seek out new developments that might have applications in Heritage Science and ensure we are active, engaged customers. Similarly, the Heritage Science community needs to be more open to technology transfer, working with industry to exploit developments made in Heritage Science so that they can have maximum impact.

The broad range of technologies, datatypes and manufacturers found in Heritage Science makes open and FAIR data particularly challenging. If the Heritage Science community can develop a shared understanding of open data under the guidance of E-RIHS, that could be a significant contribution to broader areas of science.

References

IPERION CH D.11.5 Exploitation Plan

IPERION CH D.11.6 Database of SMEs.

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5b8ae98a7&appld=PPGMS>

IPERION CH D.11.7 Web Portal of Innovation in Heritage Science.

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5b373fdc2&appld=PPGMS>

IPERION CH D.12.1 Database on CH conservation and research institutions and stakeholders.

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5ade9443d&appld=PPGMS>

IPERION CH D.12.8 Final report on sustainability strategies

E RIHS PP D.6.1 Cost Benefit Analysis and socioeconomic impact assessment.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3946206>

E RIHS PP D.6.2 Sustainability document for business plan

E RIHS PP D.9.1 First version of the E RIHS scientific vision.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3946239>

E RIHS PP D.9.2 Analysis of Innovation Background. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3946249>

E RIHS PP D.9.4 Innovation Agenda. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4288894>

IPERION HS D6.1 Data Management Plan for IPERION HS.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4541267>

IPERION HS D6.2 Exploitation Plan. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5930779>

IPERION HS Milestone 11. Interim report on documentation of instrument parameters and analysis protocols across access platforms, and metadata requirements.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7101169>